

UTILIZATION LEVEL OF PHOTOGRAPHIC IMAGE REPRESENTATION OF CHILD ABUSE FOR TEACHING SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS OF RIVERS STATE

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Abstract: The paper is on the Utilization Level of Photographic Image Representation of Child Abuse for Teaching Secondary School Students of Rivers State. One research question and one null hypothesis guided the conduct of the study. The study adopted the correlational and Ex-post facto research Design; on a population that comprised all final year students of 2019/2020 academic session offering visual arts as a subject of study in the school mentioned above. The total number of students in the population is 130. The entire population was studied. A structured questionnaire with 25 items was used to generate data from the respondents titled impact of photographic images of child abuse as instructional materials (IMPHICAIM). The instrument was subjected to face and content validity and a Cronbach Alpha reliability technique which obtained reliability indexes of .80, .88, .90, .73 and .78 respectively for each sub-scale. Then, Data on students' academic performance was extracted from the students' academic records; students were also interviewed on their experiences while on the training. Data collected were analyzed using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) to answer the research questions as well as testing the hypotheses that determine the degree of association between the variables under consideration. The study indicates that utilization of photographic image representation of child abuse correlates instructional material for teaching secondary school students of Rivers State. Therefore, there is a significant correlation between utilization of photographic image representation of child abuse and instructional material for teaching secondary school students of Rivers State. The study recommended among others that Tertiary institutions should not place students in visual arts studios/Industries that lack modern visual arts equipment and machines.

Keywords: Utilization, Photographic image representation, Child abuse, Instructional material

INTRODUCTION

The prevalent cases of child abuse in recent time has assumed an alarming rate that if urgent measures are not taken could lead to unpleasant consequences in the nearest future which might impact negatively on the cultural values and pride of the people. Reason being that instead of the trend to reduce, it is rather increasing and given birth to cultism, prostitution, drug abuse and other forms of criminality that threatens lives and properties in the Emohua Local Government Area. It is observed that in most of the secondary schools in Rivers State, teachers do not use instructional materials to teach their subjects. This act is adversely affecting studies. Child abuse has

become a global problem that needs to be tackled if children are to be given the right to education and freedom. The issue of child abuse has not been given serious attention in many parts of Nigeria and Rivers State is not left out. Given this serious attention, one would have thought that this menace will not persist. However, a retrospect on the society shows that child abuse occurs not only at home but has reared its ugly head into the school system thus creating a barrier to the attainment of sound educational development in the country (Umobong, 2019: p.462).The author affirms that in the traditional African society, the training of the child was the sole responsibility of the parents and the members of the community who had the right to discipline and correct the child whenever he goes astray. The parents trained the child in a way that is suitable and acceptable to the standard of the society (Hornby, 1988, Faruk, 2015; Fielding, 2016; Index, 2019; Kubanni, 2019 and IGI, 2019).

Following the advent of western education and the introduction of nursery and pre-primary schools, parents tend to hand over their responsibility of guiding, directing, counselling and role modeling for their children to the school. Thus, putting more demands on the school to do what the parents should do in addition to their normal school functions. Parents now push over the responsibility of caring for their children to the school. Many young children who would have been at home at about two years have been pushed over to the school. The tasks thus become enormous for the teachers and the school management to carry, leading to many children being neglected, despised and abused on daily basis. This clearly undermines the provision for the right of the child on ‘protection against indecent and inhuman treatment like abuse and neglect as earlier stated. Rather, the child has been subjected to all kinds of maltreatment, is neither protected, valued nor defended. Most times, the treatment given to young children as corrective measures constitutes one form of abuse or the other. The application of instructional resources (graphics) to present learning contents to students in Nigerian primary and junior secondary schools has been a challenging task to most teachers. Problems associated to the utilization of graphic instructional resources could stem up from different aspects – ranging from teachers’ attitude to work, dispositions of school managements to the use of instructional media, and a multitude of other factors (Clark & Starr, 1996; Faruk, 2005; Ariston, 2009 and Fielding, 2016).The author emphasized that inadequacy of skills on design of graphic resources among teachers are yet another area of concern. After the decision to present a learning content in visual form has been reached by a teacher, the problem of basic illustration techniques arise. The difficulty in physically forming an image on paper becomes so frustrating to some teachers that they give up the idea and all the potentials of visual communication is lost. The deficiency of knowledge about the principles and elements of graphic design, a nervous hand, and a dripping pen often force many teachers into the avenue of escape. Except for the few who have the advantage of training in drawing or have access to art services, creating visual image is one of the most challenging problems in teaching. Hence the above articulated issues and many more constituted the problem of this study.

Aim and Objective of the Study

The aim of the study is to determine the level of utilization of photographic images representation of child abuse to teaching secondary school students of Rivers State. The specific objective is to: determine the level of utilization of photographic image representation of child abuse to teaching secondary school students of Rivers State.

Research Question

What is the level of utilization of photographic image representation of child abuse for teaching secondary school students of Rivers State?

Research Hypothesis

There is no significant correlation between utilization of photographic image representation of child abuse and teaching secondary school students of Rivers State.

Significance of the Study

It would create awareness on the plight of child abuse in Rivers State

Definition of Terms / Abbreviations

- 1) TLM - Teaching Learning Materials
- 2) Photography - A combination of two Greek root words "Photo" and "Graphic"
- 3) Photo – Means "Light"
- 4) Graphie – writing or drawing
- 5) Da Guerretype – A name of camera
- 6) STD – Sexually Transmitted Disease
- 7) WHO – World Health Organization
- 8) S-R-C – Stimulus Response Connection
- 9) USDCDCP – United States Centres for Disease Control and Prevention
- 10) AFRUCA – Africa Unite Against Child Abuse
- 11) Pivot – Centre point on which something balance
- 12) SKILL – Ability to do something well because you have learned
- 13) FOS – A Greek Word meaning Light
- 14) Grafo – Greek word to write or draw
- 15) PPMC – Pearson Product Moment Correlation

Literature Review

Literature review here took cognizance of the contributions of important scholars on the topic above, Hornby 1998; P. 110; Wikipedia, 2006, Yanngum Hornby 1998: 2016, Vocabulary.com as well as Colin's Dictionary 2019, Cornelius, (2015 P.1) and Corensun, (2007: P.32) submitted that photography is a combination of two Greek words, photo which means "Light" and "graphic" meaning writing or drawing. Altogether, writing or drawing with light tight box, that photography from various definitions have one central idea of creating images which is a picture of someone or something. It is employed in varying fields such as sciences, business manufacturing as well as its direct uses for art, recreational purposes and mass communication. It is also one viable medium for teaching and learning in our schools. The use of images in the classroom is a pedagogical strategy aimed as engaging students who grown up in media – rich environment. Images in classroom has led to increased student interactivity and visual literacy skills, which contribute to their overall critical thinking, skills and life – long learning. Several authors have viewed photographic images from the service it renders in the society. For instance, Ross, (1996), Lindsay, 1913 and Mayer, 2005), Encyclopedia Britannic, (2019), Aizybyfek, (2019) state that photographic images are generally expressed by different modes of graphic design approaches for visual representations. That images that are recorded are formed by a lens in a camera. That images that are generated by a computer are called computer graphics. However, photographic images used in teaching serve as instructional materials that facilitates better assimilation of lesson delivery. The authors that spouse on instructional materials are (Liwis, 2018, IGI Global, (2019), and Aginna-Obu, 2005). They all expressed that instructional materials refers to the human and non-human materials and facilities that can easily be used to

promote teaching and learning activities. In designing instructional material, the focus should center on the learner than the teacher. Indeed, there is no empirical evidence to show that photographic image of child abuse as instructional materials in teaching students in junior secondary schools in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State has been investigated before now. There is therefore the need to bridge this gap in research on the topic of the study (Ross, 1996, Mayer, 2005; Merriam-W, 2019; Tolmachev, 2019 and Vocabulary.com, 2019).

Research Methodology

Area of the Study

This study focused in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State. Emohua Local Government Area is one of the four Local Government Areas of Ikwerre ethnic nationalities in Rivers State. Emohua was chosen to be the area of the study due to the abysmal of child abuse cases that are witnessed in the area in recent times, children that should be in school are on the streets doing nothing during school hours, and also sending children of school age to go to farm during schools hours among others.

Population of the Study

A study or research population is generally refer to the entire group of persons or objects or organizations collected under the area of study. The population of this research study comprised the twenty-five (25) junior secondary schools in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State, Nigeria. With the total figure of 8,759 students and teacher, male 4,301, female 3,917 and teachers 541 (Source; Admin office Emohua Education Authority).

Sample and Sampling Technique

Out of the total population, 700 Teachers and Students in junior secondary school class three (J.S.S 3) within the secondary schools in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State were sampled for the study. Simple balloting techniques was used to pick 10 students from each of the public junior secondary schools, which form the sample size for the study. The balloting was made by the use of papers marked yes and no folded and reshuffled in a small container, the students were asked to pick one of the papers. Those who picked “yes” were used; while those that picked “no” were dropped.

Instrument for Data Collection

The instrument for data collection was a well-structured questionnaire designed by the researcher to elicit responses from the respondents concerning impact of photographic images of child abuse as instructional materials (IMPHICAIM) for teaching secondary students of Rivers State. The questionnaire items were based on 4 points likert scale strongly agree, agree, disagree and strongly disagree. The responses from the respondents from the questionnaire provided the necessary data that were used for the analysis.

Reliability of the Instrument

For this study to ensure that the survey instrument was reliable; a test method was used on 15 samples that did not take part in the study. The scores was treated to Pearson product moment correlation co-efficient (PPMC). The resultant value of 0.92 were converted using: the spearman Brown Predicted formula to have reliability co-efficient of 0.78. The instrument was therefore considered reliable.

Method of Data Analysis

To establish the relationship between variables, the information collected were turned to data which were analyzed using Pearson’s Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMC) to test the relationship existing between impacts of photographic image of child abuse for teaching secondary school students of Rivers State. The

responses from the questionnaire were used on four points Likert scale and frequency count point. Weights that were assigned to the scales as follows:

Strongly Agree (SA)	1 point
Agree (A)	2 point
Strongly Disagree (SD)	4 point
Disagree (D)	3 points

Plate 1: Street Child

Photograph size (20cmx16cm)

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This child feeds for himself, selling pure water is one of the various means he makes a living. Family, friends and Government have distant themselves from him. He cannot kill himself.

Presentation of Data and Discussion

Answering of Research Question

Research Question: What is the correlation between utilization of photographic image representation of child abuse and instructional material for teaching secondary school students of Rivers State?

Table 1: Summary of relationship test between utilization of photographic image representation of child abuse and instructional material for teaching.

Variables	$\sum X$ $\sum Y$	$\sum X^2$ $\sum Y^2$	$\sum XY$	r_{cal}
Utilization of photographic image representation of child abuse	1715	4375	5635	0.486
Instructional material for teaching	2345	8155		

The result from Table 1 shows the summary of the Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) of the relationship between utilization of photographic image representation of child abuse and instructional material for teaching in junior secondary schools. The result of the analysis shows an r-value of 0.486. This indicates that utilization of photographic image representation of child abuse correlates instructional material for teaching in junior secondary schools in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Testing of Null Hypothesis

Null Hypothesis: There is no significant correlation between utilization of photographic image representation of child abuse and instructional material for teaching in junior secondary schools in Emohua Local Government Area.

Table 2: Summary of PPMC significant relationship test between utilization of photographic image representation of child abuse and instructional material for teaching

Variables	$\sum X$ $\sum Y$	$\sum X^2$ $\sum Y^2$	$\sum XY$	r_{cal}	Df	r_{crit}	Decision
Utilization of photographic image representation of child abuse	1715	4375	5635	0.486	698	0.139	Reject Null Hypothesis
Instructional material for teaching	2345	8155					

Summary of result in table 2 indicates that with a df of 698 and at 0.05 level of significance, the calculated value of r (0.484) is greater than the critical value of r (0.139), which leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis. Therefore, there is a significant correlation between utilization of photographic image representation of child abuse and instructional material for teaching secondary school students of Rivers State.

Summary of Findings

There is a significant correlation between utilization of photographic image representation of child abuse and instructional material for teaching in junior secondary schools in Emohua Local Government Area.

Discussion of Findings

Correlation between Utilization of Photographic Image Representation of Child Abuse and Instructional Material for Teaching Secondary School Students of Rivers State.

The result in hypothesis three reveals and indicates that with a df of 698 and at 0.05 level of significance, the calculated value of r (0.484) is greater than the critical value of r (0.139), which leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis. Therefore, there is a significant correlation between utilization of photographic image representation of child abuse and teaching secondary school students of Rivers State. This finding corroborates the views of Faruk (2005) who reveals that problems associated to the utilization of graphic instructional resources could stem up from different aspects – ranging from teachers’ attitude to work, dispositions of school managements to use of instructional media, and a multitude of other factors. This fact proves that ineffective utilization is also a factor affecting effective use of photographic images of child abuse.

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